

TECHNICAL REPORT
GRIAL-TR-2017-004
JULY 2017

SEEQ survey adapted to ahMOOC

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RECOMMENDED CITATION

Fidalgo-Blanco, Á., Sein-Echaluce Lacleta, M. L., & García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2017). *SEQ survey adapted to ahMOOC*. (Technical Report GRIAL-TR-2017-004). Salamanca, Spain: Grupo GRIAL. <https://repositorio.grial.eu/handle/grial/920>. doi:10.5281/zenodo.823699

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1. Introduction

The research groups LITI (<http://www.liti.es>), GIDTIC (<http://gidtic.com>) and GRIAL (<http://grial.usal.es>) are working on new MOOC (Massive Online Open Courses) models [1-19], combining innovation in both pedagogical and technological issues.

The last proposal is the adaptive hybrid MOOC model (ahMOOC) [20], we have adapted the SEEQ (Student Evaluation of Educational Quality - <http://teaching.usask.ca/classes/course-evaluations.php#SEEQ>) questionnaire [21] to use it with MOOC in order to measure Learning (Q1 to Q4), Enthusiasm (Q5 to Q8), Contents (Q9, Q10), Organization (Q11 to Q17) and Evaluation (Q18 to Q21). Table 1 also shows the value obtained (in percentage) from the responses for each element of the Likert scale (1 to 4), (1 – do not agree, 2 – slightly agree, 3 – mostly agree, 4 – totally agree).

2. Questionnaire

	<i>Items/percentages</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>
Q1	<i>I understood and leaned from the contents of the course</i>	0.49	4.93	26.60	67.98
Q2	<i>In this course, I learned valuable things</i>	0.49	1.48	27.59	70.44
Q3	<i>My interest in some topics has increased while doing this course</i>	0.49	3.45	29.06	67.00
Q4	<i>This course was stimulating</i>	0.99	6.90	33.00	59.11
Q5	<i>The course was active and dynamic</i>	1.48	9.36	43.84	45.32
Q6	<i>The way contents were presented maintained my attention</i>	0.00	9.85	33.50	56.65
Q7	<i>Generally speaking, the videos that were included were interesting</i>	0.49	9.36	31.03	59.11
Q8	<i>I participated often and worked actively</i>	1.48	12.81	49.26	36.45
Q9	<i>The course materials were well designed</i>	1.48	5.91	27.09	65.52
Q10	<i>Video explanations were clear and helpful for understanding the topics of the course</i>	0.99	4.93	23.65	70.44
Q11	<i>The information shared by participants was useful for understanding concepts</i>	4.93	23.15	40.39	31.53
Q12	<i>The design of a course that adapts to the needs of participants was well executed</i>	0.00	4.43	30.54	65.02
Q13	<i>The fact that resources were visible depending on my learning pace was useful</i>	1.48	4.43	24.63	69.46
Q14	<i>My objectives when starting the course were the same as those I ultimately reached</i>	0.99	6.90	43.84	48.28
Q15	<i>The suggested activities improved the learning of the course contents</i>	0.99	8.37	30.54	60.10
Q16	<i>The suggested activities produced useful content once the course was over</i>	1.97	7.39	30.05	60.59
Q17	<i>Resources and shared ideas in the blog or forum provided different points of view from those given by the teachers</i>	4.43	15.27	44.83	35.47
Q18	<i>The evaluation difficulty was adequate</i>	0.99	3.94	31.03	41.38
Q19	<i>The evaluation activities helped me to evaluate my progress in the course</i>	1.97	9.85	27.59	37.93
Q20	<i>The evaluation method was suitable for this type of course</i>	1.97	8.37	39.41	50.25
Q21	<i>The relationship between the effort invested and the obtained goals was appropriate</i>	0.49	4.43	36.95	58.13

Acknowledgments

Authors would like to express their gratitude to the research groups (LITI, <http://www.liti.es>; GIDTIC, <http://gidtic.com> and GRIAL, <http://grial.usal.es>). This work has been partially funded by the Spanish Government Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness throughout the DEFINES project (Ref. TIN2016-80172-R).

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